

Soft Metric Spaces and its Development: A comprehensive Review

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Abstract: The aim of this present research paper to study brief about soft set, soft metric space and some applications in the field of fixed point theory. The studied results will concern with solution of uncertainty problems in real life.

Mathematics subject classification: 47H10.

Keywords: Soft sets, soft metric spaces, fixed point, common fixed point, fuzzy soft metric spaces.

I. Introduction

In general, mathematics have some methods to solve our real-life problem but all the methods are applicable only on crisp or precise data. It is very difficult to solve some problem which has vagueness or not clear or uncertainty. For dealing such problem mathematicians develop new theories such as fuzzy theory, probability theory, rough set and many more. But all have some limitations which all methods bring with them. To overcome these limitations in 1999 Molodtsov introduce new concept and named it soft set. Soft set can deal with ambiguity and vagueness in better manner. It is nothing but a family of parameters and power set of subsets. It has capability to solve problem of many fields like engineering, economic, medical etc.

The concept of set “collection of well define object” is initially introduce by George cantor in 1800 and it named as classical set theory. Classical set theory can only deal with yes or no and is puts limit on them to overcome this limitation in 1965 L. Zadeh introduce new concept which have more power than classical set theory to deal with uncertainty or vagueness and named it fuzzy set theory [19]. After fuzzy set theory Pawlak introduce new concept rough set which is deal with uncertainty in better manner than fuzzy logic in 1982 [20]. And after all of this D. Molodtsov introduce very fresh concept soft set theory which is parameterized family in 1999 and change the direction of research toward itself [21].

The theory presented by molodtsov make huge impact on researchers all are wanted to work on this bombastic area. In this manner maji et al. done a great work by proving several operations on soft set theory and make path of applications in decision making problem by rough mathematics in 2003 [22, 23] but in this research paper D. Chen found a glitch in soft set reduction which they offered in their work in 2005 [24] and preset a new definition of soft set parametrization reduction and comparison. M. Shabir and M. Naz present a new concept of soft topological space which are defined over an initial universe with parameters of fixed set and many notions like soft open set and closed set etc. in 2011 [26]. This work stablishes as milestone for researcher of this area. After such a work S. Das and S.K. Samanta give a new breakthrough in 2013 by introducing notion of soft metric space which is basically based on soft point of soft sets and also show soft metric space is soft topological space [27].

Researcher found this soft set theory very effective tool for dealing with uncertainty so they try to blend this with other theories. In this manner T. Beaula and C. Gunaseeli introduced a new concept of fuzzy soft point and by this they derived fuzzy soft metric space and also, they gave some properties of this to establish it in 2014 [28]. After this T. Beaula and M. M. Priyanga present fuzzy soft normed linear space by using of soft normed linear space and fuzzy normed linear space. In 2022 A. Mishra, R. Bhardwaj and N. Joshi give a tremendous use of fuzzy soft set. They show use of fuzzy soft set in defence sector by using of D-S theory and weighted average combination rule. This work gives a algorithm to separate a node to destabilize a terrorist network [13]. In 2023 Sonam, Ramakant Bhardwaj and S. Narayan blend Banach contraction principle with soft points and stablish Banach contraction principle in soft fuzzy metric space between the soft points of soft set and also, they gave some examples for support their work [11]. Sonam, V. Rathore, A. Pal, R. Bhardwaj and S. Narayan present study of fixed point in orthogonal fuzzy metric space, mainly they focus on investigation of uniqueness of Fixed point for self-mapping that satisfy an implicit relation condition within the framework of complete orthogonal fuzzy metric spaces [9]. S. Ghosh, Sonam, R. Bhardwaj and S. Narayan in 2024 try to fusing neutrosophic to fuzzy metric space and named this novel concept as neutrosophic fuzzy metric space also they gave some topological properties of the concept which is introduced [7]. P. Patel, B. Saxena, R. Bhardwaj and Sonam in 2024 did a new work which uses some mathematical techniques like Banach contraction principle, rational mapping and iterative method. under newly defined rational contractions they show fixed point results for distinct function [4]. In 2024 D. sarkar, R. Bhardwaj, V. Rathore and P. Konar use G-presic type multi-valued mapping for presenting best proximity results and this result is extension of G-presic theorem and also, they gave some illustrations for their work [8]. Sonam and R. Bhardwaj investigate a new concept when they did this work triangular property of fuzzy bipolar metric space is considered and explored fuzzy bipolar metric space also, they show this work can be used in existence and uniqueness of solution to non-linear integral equation and this work sees as boom for researcher of this field [1]. S. Ghosh, R. Bhardwaj, S. Narayan and Sonam in 2025 show newly defined neutrosophic fuzzy metric space for some basic fixed-point theorems like Edelstein fixed point

theorem, Banach fixed point theorem and Kannan fixed point theorem. In this work Kannan fixed point theorem categorized into two-part Kannan and Kannan fixed point theorems also they show semi metric in these spaces and this work is very new, no one did this type of work in this particular area [3].

II. Methodology

Definition2.1: Let Z be a universal set and set of parameters is P . Then the pair of (f, P) is called soft set over Z only when $f: P \rightarrow P(Z)$ that is f is mapped from P into power set of Z .

Example1:

Imagine a person is looking to buy a bullock cart and considers various factors like "wooden quality," "wheel," "juda balancing," "dimension," "safety guard," "design," and "muscularity of bull".

Universal set(U)= let us assume the businessman is considering five bullock carts:

- X1: cart A
- X2: cart B
- X3: cart C
- X4: cart D
- X5: cart E

Set of parameters (attributes) is $E = \{\text{wooden quality, wheel, juda balancing, dimension, safety guard, design, and muscularity of bull}\}$

A soft set (F, E) is defined where F maps each parameter to a subset of U .

- $F(\text{wooden quality}): -e1$
- $F(\text{wheel}): -e2$
- $F(\text{juda balancing}): -e3$
- $F(\text{dimension}): -e4$
- $F(\text{safety guard}): -e5$
- $F(\text{design}): -e6$
- $F(\text{muscularity of bull}): -e7$

Therefore, the soft set (F, E) can be represented as:

- $F(\text{wooden quality}) = F(e1) = \{X1, X2, X4\}$
- $F(\text{wheel}) = F(e2) = \{X1, X3, X5\}$
- $F(\text{juda balancing}) = F(e3) = \{X2, X3, X4\}$
- $F(\text{dimension}) = F(e4) = \{X1, X5\}$
- $F(\text{safety guard}) = F(e5) = \{X2, X5\}$
- $F(\text{design}) = F(e6) = \{X1, X3, X4\}$
- $F(\text{muscularity of bull}) = F(e7) = \{X2, X3, X5\}$.

	e_1	e_2	e_3	e_4	e_5	e_6	e_7
Cart A	1	1	0	1	0	1	0
Cart B	1	0	1	0	1	0	1
Cart C	0	1	1	0	0	1	1
Cart D	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Cart E	0	1	0	1	1	0	1

Definition2.2: let (f, P) and (g, Q) be two soft set over Z , (f, P) is said to be subset of (g, Q) if,

$(f, P) \subseteq (g, Q)$ if $f(\varepsilon) \subseteq g(\varepsilon) \forall \varepsilon \in P$ and they are equal if $(f, P) \subseteq (g, Q)$ and $(g, Q) \subseteq (f, P)$.

Definition2.3: let (f, P) and (g, Q) be two soft set over Z and intersection of these two soft sets is (h, R) , where R is intersection of P and Q , $h(e) = f(e) \cap g(e), \forall e \in R$, the relationship of intersection denoted by $(f, P) \cap (g, Q) = (h, R)$.

Definition2.4: let (f, P) and (g, Q) be two soft set over Z and the union of these two soft sets is (h, R) , where R is union of P and $Q, \forall e \in R$,

$$h(e) \begin{cases} f(e), & \text{if } e \in P - Q \\ g(e), & \text{if } e \in Q - P \\ f(e) \cup g(e), & e \in P \cap Q \end{cases}$$

the relationship of union denoted by $(f, P) \cup (g, Q) = (h, R)$.

Definition2.5: A soft set (f, P) over Z is null soft set if $f(e) = \emptyset, \forall e \in P$, and it is denoted by \emptyset .

Definition2.6: A soft set (f, P) over Z is absolute soft set if $f(e) = Z, \forall e \in P$

And it is denoted by \tilde{Z} .

Definition2.7: let (f, P) and (g, P) be two soft set over Z and (h, P) is difference of these two soft is defined as $h(e) = f(e) \setminus g(e), \forall e \in P$ the relationship of difference denoted by $(f, P) \setminus (g, P)$.

Definition2.8: $(f, P)^c$ is called complement of (f, P) over Z and it can be defined as $(f, P)^c = (f^c, P)$, where $f^c: A \rightarrow P(Z)$ is a mapping given by $f^c(\varepsilon) = Z - f(\varepsilon), \forall \varepsilon$.

Definition2.9: Let R be the set of real numbers and $B(R)$ be the collection of all non-empty bounded subsets of R and P be taken as a set of parameters then a mapping $f: P \rightarrow B(R)$ is called a soft real set. If a real soft set is a singleton soft set, it will be called a soft real number and denoted by $\tilde{p}, \tilde{q}, \tilde{r}$ etc. $\tilde{0}$ and $\tilde{1}$ are the soft real numbers where $\tilde{0}(\varepsilon) = 0, \tilde{1}(\varepsilon) = 1, \forall \varepsilon \in P$ respectively.

Definition2.10: Let \tilde{p} and \tilde{q} are two soft real numbers. Then the following statements holds:

- $\tilde{p} \lesssim \tilde{q}$ if $\tilde{p}(\varepsilon) \lesssim \tilde{q}(\varepsilon) \forall \varepsilon \in P;$
- $\tilde{p} \gtrsim \tilde{q}$ if $\tilde{p}(\varepsilon) \gtrsim \tilde{q}(\varepsilon) \forall \varepsilon \in P;$
- $\tilde{p} < \tilde{q}$ if $\tilde{p}(\varepsilon) < \tilde{q}(\varepsilon) \forall \varepsilon \in P;$
- $\tilde{p} > \tilde{q}$ if $\tilde{p}(\varepsilon) > \tilde{q}(\varepsilon) \forall \varepsilon \in P;$

Definition2.11: A soft set (f, P) over Z is said to be a soft point, then it is denoted by \tilde{a}_ε , for some $\varepsilon \in P, f(\varepsilon) = \{a\}$ and $f(\tilde{\varepsilon}) = \emptyset \forall \tilde{\varepsilon} \in P / \{\varepsilon\}$.

Definition2.12: \tilde{a}_ε and \tilde{b}_ε are two soft points and both of them equal if $\varepsilon = \tilde{\varepsilon}$ and $a = b$. Thus $\tilde{a}_\varepsilon \neq \tilde{b}_\varepsilon \Leftrightarrow a \neq b$ or $\varepsilon \neq \tilde{\varepsilon}$.

Definition2.13: All soft sets can be written as a union of all soft points which contain in it and denoted by $(f, P) =$

$\cup_{\tilde{a}_\varepsilon \in (f,P)} \tilde{a}_\varepsilon$. Conversely a collection of soft points may be regarded as a soft set.

Definition2.14: A mapping $\varphi: SP(\tilde{\mu}) \times SP(\tilde{\mu}) \rightarrow R(P)^*$ is said to be a soft metric on the soft set $\tilde{\mu}$ if φ satisfies the following conditions:

- $\varphi(\tilde{a}_\varepsilon, \tilde{b}_\varepsilon) \geq \tilde{0} \forall \tilde{a}_\varepsilon, \tilde{b}_\varepsilon \in \tilde{\mu}$,
- $\varphi(\tilde{a}_\varepsilon, \tilde{b}_\varepsilon) = \tilde{0} \Leftrightarrow \tilde{a}_\varepsilon = \tilde{b}_\varepsilon$,
- $\varphi(\tilde{a}_\varepsilon, \tilde{b}_\varepsilon) = \varphi(\tilde{b}_\varepsilon, \tilde{a}_\varepsilon) \forall \tilde{a}_\varepsilon, \tilde{b}_\varepsilon \in \tilde{\mu}$
- $\varphi(\tilde{a}_\varepsilon, \tilde{c}_{\varepsilon II}) \leq \varphi(\tilde{a}_\varepsilon, \tilde{b}_\varepsilon) + \varphi(\tilde{b}_\varepsilon, \tilde{c}_{\varepsilon II}) \forall \tilde{a}_\varepsilon, \tilde{b}_\varepsilon, \tilde{c}_{\varepsilon II} \in \tilde{\mu}$

The soft set $\tilde{\mu}$ with a soft metric φ on $\tilde{\mu}$ is said to be soft metric space and it is denoted by $(\tilde{\mu}, \varphi, P)$.

Definition2.15: A soft topological space $(\tilde{\mu}, \tau, P)$ over $\tilde{\mu}$, then $(f, P)^\circ$ is said to be soft interior of (f, P) and is defined as union of all soft open sets which belong to (f, P) .

Definition2.16: A soft topological space $(\tilde{\mu}, \tau, P)$ over $\tilde{\mu}$, then $\overline{(f, P)}$ is said to be soft closure of (f, P) and is defined as intersection of all soft closed sets which belong to (f, P) .

III. Conclusion

This review puts light on the development and significance of soft metric spaces, which merge soft set theory with classical metric concepts to better handle ambiguity, uncertainty and imprecision. We discussed key definitions, properties, and recent extensions, showing how soft metric spaces have evolved year by year and found areas of relevance like decision-making, topology, and computer science.

In the present work, we show soft theory and its applications in diverse fields, how it applicable in different scenario and how much potential it has to solve uncertainty problems.

IV. Future Scope

This research may give better understanding to new researcher of this area to build their work. As research continues, soft metric spaces are expected to play an increasingly important role in modelling complex systems and uncertain data. Their ongoing development opens up promising opportunities for both theoretical exploration and practical application.

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